

The code for gain compensated type 3 PLL and the parameters used for the simulation data are addressed in this data availability statement.

1. code required for generating bode plot and root locus through matlab live editor for the proposed gain compensated type 3 PLL is addressed here.

```
%% variable assignment for type 2 and type 3 PLLs
```

```
kp=114;
ki=6634.6;
%
V=1;
k=1;
k1=2;
k2=5;
k3=10;
k4=25;
k5=0.2;
k6=0.1;
s=tf('s');
%
LF=(kp*s+ki)/s;
pure_integrator=1/s;
OLTF_type2_PLL=V*LF*pure_integrator;
CLTF_type2_PLL=feedback(OLTF_type2_PLL,1);
%%
mu0=96.7;
mu1=8511;
mu2=187296;
G=1;
LF_1=(mu0*s^2+mu1*s+mu2)/s^2;
OLTF_type3_PLL=V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
GC_type3_PLL=G*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
CLTF_type3_PLL=feedback(OLTF_type3_PLL,1);
ErrorTF_type3_PLL = feedback(1, OLTF_type3_PLL);
ErrorTF_GC_PLL = feedback(1, GC_type3_PLL);
check = CLTF_type3_PLL + ErrorTF_type3_PLL;
minreal(check)
%%
K=k*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
K1=k1*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
K2=k2*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
K3=k3*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
K4=k4*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
K5=k5*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
K6=k6*V*LF_1*pure_integrator;
%%
CK = feedback(K, 1);
CK1 = feedback(K1, 1);
CK2 = feedback(K2, 1);
CK3 = feedback(K3,1);
CK4 = feedback(K4,1);
CK5 = feedback(K5,1);
CK6 = feedback(K6,1);
%%
```

```

figure(1);
rlocus(OLTF_type2_PLL);
grid on;

figure(2);
rlocus(OLTF_type3_PLL);
grid on;
%%
figure(3);
bode(K, 'r', K1, 'k', K2, 'b', K3, 'm', K4, 'g', K5, 'k--');
grid on;

```

2. Appendix

Parameter	Value
Rated voltage and frequency	415 V (L-L), 50Hz
Sampling Time	$T_s = 10 \mu s$
Linear Load	6 kW+jkVAR
Interfacing Inductance	$L_{se} = L_{sh} = 4 mH$
Series Ripple Filter	$R_f = 5 \Omega, C_f = 30 \mu f$
DC-link Capacitor	4700 μf
DC-link voltage	700 V
DC-link voltage PI controller	$K_{ps} = 260, K_{is} = 0.012$
MSTOGI filter gains	m=1.414
Loop filter parameters	$\mu_0 = 96.7/G_c, \mu_1 = 8511/G_c$ and $\mu_2 = 187296/G_c$
Single phase transformer rating	5 KVA
Transformer turns ratio	230:115
Grid inductance (L_s)	1 mH
Grid Compensation (G_c)	2.1